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ABSTRACT

The bay of Béago is located on the northern shore of the Ebrié lagoon. This bay, used for fishing, navigation and sand dredging, has also become a receptacle for macro-waste. Sand mining and the discharge of pollutants into the bay of Béago could lead to a change in its morphology. To participate in the preservation of this bay, this work aims to know its morpho-bathymetric characteristics. A bathymetric survey was carried out in the bay using a Lowrance echo sounder. The data were processed with Surfer software. West-East radials were used to identify the types of channels in the bay. The depths are between 0 and 14 m. The bottom of the bay is generally flat but is present in places by depressions and shoals. The channels are of the "intermediate" and "V" types.

KEYWORDS: Bay, Morpho-bathymetric, Macrowaste, Channels, Ebrié Lagoon

1. INTRODUCTION

The Ebrié lagoon is a brackish body of water of 532 km², located in one of the coastal depressions of Côte d'Ivoire. It is bordered by many bays including that of Béago (Figure 1). With a watershed of 41 km², the bay of Béago has an area of 34.19 ha. This bay is one of the most anthropized bays of the Ebrié lagoon. The importance of the bay of Béago is multiple. Indeed, it is used for fishing, canoeing, transport and dredging of sand. The bay of Béago is bordered in some places by mangroves, a habitat for crustaceans and certain birds. Anthropogenic activities discharge macro-waste into the bay of Béago. It is also subject to silting due to land exploitation on its banks. These different anthropogenic forces could lead to a modification of the morphology of the bottom of the bay. In order to contribute to the preservation of this bay and facilitate movement on this body of water, this study aims to know its morpho-bathymetric characteristics.

Figure (1) Location of Béago bay

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1- Bathymetric surveys and correction of probe data

The bathymetric surveys, carried out in the bay of Béago, consist of measuring the depth of the body of water by determining the distance between the surface and the bottom of the water section. The operation made it possible to carry out 6320 probes. The echo sounder used for this activity is of the Lowrance type. It is coupled with a Garmin type GPS.

The real depth of the bay of Béago is obtained after two corrections. They are made on the raw data from the sensors called type 1 data. The first correction is based on adding to the depth given by the echo sounder sensor (type 1 data) the immersion depth of the transducer to obtain type 2 data. The second correction makes it possible to subtract the tidal range from the type 2 data [1]. These treatments make it possible to reduce the margins of error and determine the actual depth measured at each sounding point (Figure 2). The different corrections can be translated by the following equation [2]:

$$P_r = P_e + P_{it} \pm M \quad (i)$$

Where P_r is the actual depth, P_e the depth given by the echo sounder, P_{it} the immersion depth of the transducer and M the tidal range.

The bathymetric map of Béago bay was made using Surfer 13 software. Graphic files are created using the data files. The interpolation method is kriging. It allows obtaining digital terrain models (DTM).

Figure (2) Probe positioning map

3. RESULTS

3.1- Bathymetric map of Béago bay

Depths vary from 0 to 14 m; with an average of 6 m (Figure 3). The North-East and South-East areas allow us to observe the highest depth values. On the other hand, the shallow depths are mainly observed towards the banks and at the southern entrance of the bay. The digital terrain model allows us to observe depressions and a relatively flat bottom (Figure 4). The largest depressions are located in the Center and South between latitudes 587000 to 586900 m and longitudes 381600 to 381800 m. The shoals are located in the South-West and North-East between latitudes 587500 to 587300 m and longitudes 381700 to 381800 m.

Figure (3) 2D bathymetric map of Béago Bay

Figure (4) Digital terrain model (3D) of Béago Bay

3.2- Channel variation

Nine radials (P1 to P9) are drawn in parallel in an East-West direction and perpendicular to the main channel of the bay (Figure 5). The profiles from these radials show channels of the “V” type (P3 and P7) and intermediate type (P1, P2, P4, P5, P6, P8 and P9). The intermediate type channels are in the majority compared to the “V” channels. Figure 6 shows the “V” channels and Figure 7 the intermediate channels.

Figure (5) Radial positioning map

Figure (6) "V" type profile

Figure (7) "Intermediate" type profiles

4. DISCUSSION

4.1- Depth variation

The depths in Béago bay vary between 0 and 14 m. This variation in depth is thought to be linked to natural pressures (lagoon current) and anthropogenic pressures (discharge of macro-waste into the bay, sand mining and backfilling). The average depth is 6 m in Béago bay. In Adiopodoumé bay, it is 2.5 m [3]. The average depth in Béago bay is higher than that of Adiopodoumé bay. This difference is thought to be due to the effects of anthropogenic activities, which are thought to be greater in Béago Bay compared to Adiopodoumé Bay. Indeed, the latter is one of the least anthropogenic bays in the Ebrié lagoon. The maximum depth in Béago bay is 14 m; whereas it is 25.4 m at the level of Bingerville bay [4]. The difference between these two maximum depths is 11.4 m. This could be explained by intensive sand mining in Bingerville bay compared to Béago bay and also by the low discharge of macro-waste in Bingerville bay compared to Béago bay.

4.2- 2D Bathymetric Profile

Two types of channels were observed in Béago bay. The "V" type channels and the intermediate type channels. The "V" type channels are the result of an erosion process [5]. They are due to the transformation of the relief by currents and especially sand exploitation. The intermediate type channels are in full transformation, under the effect of accumulation and erosion agents, to reach their equilibrium shape [6;7].

4.3- Digital Terrain Model

The 3D bathymetric map made it possible to observe a generally flat bottom but depressions and shoals are present in places. A generally flat bottom morphology suggests a tendency towards deposition [8]. The depressions are due to intense sand dredging activities or the effect of currents [3]. They are favorable areas for navigation. The presence of shoals reflects a deposit of sediments in a calm environment [2].

5. CONCLUSION

The morphology of the bottom of Béago bay is generally flat, with depths varying between 0 and 14 m. Depressions and shoals are observed in certain places. They testify to the combined effect of erosion, sand dredging and sediment deposition in the bay. The channels observed in Béago bay are mainly of the intermediate type. They have not yet reached their equilibrium stage. The "V" type channels observed in the minority in the bay indicate an erosion-transport phenomenon.

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